

Velocity Dependent Potential and Quantum Phase

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If a Lagrangian contains a potential dependent on dx/dt , it is possible this does not contribute to the classical equations of motion. Nevertheless, the fact that the potential is present suggests there is a physical impact. A different Lagrangian yielding the same equations of motion, does not necessarily represent the same physical situation i.e. the equations of motion do not uniquely determine a physical situation. In particular, using the Lagrange formalism yields momentum $p = dL / d(dx/dt)$ which may contain the usual $m dx/dt$ term plus terms from velocity related potentials.

We argued in previous notes, that for quantum mechanics there is a momentum distribution at each x point which yields an average $pp/2m$ at x . Moving from one x to another yields a change in pp indicating an average acceleration. The potential $V(x)$, it was argued, may be written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, it is stochastic, yielding momentum hits of k which only yield a force $-dV/dx$ on average. Given that average acceleration is stochastic, average momentum should also be stochastic. For the case of a potential $A(x)dx/dt$, the Lagrangian momentum $dL/d(dx/dt) = m dx/dt + A(x)$. dx/dt is an average of stochastic value i.e. $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, but $A(x)$ is also stochastic i.e. $A(x) = \sum_k A_k \exp(ikx)$. One may combine the two terms to create a term of the form $b_k \exp(ijx)$. We argue that this contains the combined stochasticity of p and $A(x)$. Special considerations show that if $W(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$, then one may break out $W_1(x)$ as a phase related directly to $A(x)$ i.e. $W_1(x) = \exp\{i \int_{(0,x)} A(x) dx\}$ which is experimentally observable.

Lagrangian Considerations

The classical Lagrangian $L=T-V$ is usually used to calculate the classical equations of motion, but we argue that it contains more physics than these equations. In particular, two different Lagrangians may yield the same equations of motion. For example, adding $A(x) dx/dt$ or $d/dt [\int_{0,x} f(t) dx]$ to a Lagrangian does not change the equations of motion as there is cancellation of various pieces related to these terms. This cancellation, however, may represent physics present in the system. The equations of motion do not uniquely define a physical system. For example, one may have a particle at rest and one at rest with a force to the right and left which cancel.

If one considers the simple case: $m dx/dt dx/dt + V(x) = E$ ((1)), one may vary $x \rightarrow x+dt$ dx/dt and $dx/dt \rightarrow dx/dt + dt d/dt dx/dt$. Keeping first order variations in ((1)) and balancing them yields:

$$m dt dx/dt d/dt dx/dt + dV/dx dx/dt dt = 0 \quad ((2))$$

which is Newton's second law. Thus, a change in dx/dt balances one in x . If a potential contains both dx/dt and x , both change. There is a term related to $d/dt dx/dt dt$ and one to $dt dx/dt$. It is possible that these two terms cancel. In such a case, the potential does not change the classical

equations of motion, but still represents physics present in the system. Two such potentials are $A(x)dx/dt$ and $d/dt [\int V(x) dx]$. Given that kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}m(dx/dt)^2$ changes as $d/dt dx/dt$, one may combine the change in potential related to $d/dt dx/dt$ with $m(dx/dt)^2$ to obtain a term proportional to $d/dt dx/dt$. This is the Lagrangian momentum $dL/d(dx/dt)$. The minus sign in the Lagrangian $L=T-V$ allows for the $d/dt dx/dt$ potential piece to cancel with the $d/dt dx/dt$ piece.

Consider a potential $A(x) dx/dt$ which may change due to changes in x and dx/dt . Simply writing $A(x + dt dx/dt) \{ dx/dt + dt d/dt dx/dt \}$ yields first order change terms of:

$$A(x) dt d/dt dx/dt \quad \text{and} \quad dA/dx dt dx/dt dx/dt = dA/dx dx/dt dx$$

Integrating the first term by parts allows for it to “cancel” with the second, thus leading to a potential which does not affect the classical equations of motion.

Quantum Mechanics and Stochasticity

We argued in previous notes that bound state quantum mechanics is based on stochastic hits from a potential $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ which produces a momentum distribution at each x i.e. $P(p/x)= \exp(ipx) a(p) / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction. On average, kinetic energy at x i.e. $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W = 1/2m \sum_p p^2 a(p) \exp(ipx) / W$ which is equivalent to the classical result $KE(x)$. Kinetic energy is an average quantity. There are two “average” momenta, the rms momenta and $-id/dx W / W$. Acceleration manifests itself through the changing of the momentum distribution (and hence average kinetic energy) as one moves from x to $x+dx$.

In creating a momentum distribution i.e. $P(p/x)$, we assume a statistical situation in which one has free particles with different momenta. A stochastic hit from $V(x)$ i.e. from a piece $V_k \exp(ikx)$ changes the momentum of the particle. For a free quantum particle with no potential, a statistical situation is also assumed, namely that the particle may be at any x with the same probability or $P(x)= \text{constant}$. This probability, however, does not contain any stochasticity which quantum mechanics seems to represent even for the case of a free particle. The $\exp(ipx)$ has a modulus of 1 and could represent stochasticity as well as an overall $P(x)=\text{constant}$. The idea seems to be that for a free particle with constant momentum p , p is really an average as there are periodic fluctuations occurring, represented by $\exp(ipx)$. (Some references ascribe $\exp(ipx)$ to zitterbewegung.) This might appear to be a little unusual, but if one considers a quantum particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls, a solution is $\sin(pave x)$. $Pave$ is an average momentum, all momenta are involved, but on average it seems as if the particle is a combination of $\exp(ipave x)$ and $\exp(-ipave x)$.

The Case of $-A(x) dx/dt$

Using the Lagrangian momentum $dL/ d(dx/dt) = m(dx/dt) + A(x)$ for the potential $-A(x) dx/dt$ shows that there are two stochastic terms. The first is:

$$m dx/dt = m \sum_{p_1} a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) / W_0(x) \quad ((3a))$$

And the second: $A(x) = \sum_k A_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((3b))$

It seems one should be able to combine these into one term and obtain a generalized wavefunction dependent on a “momentum” which no longer represents the particle momentum $m dx/dt$, but a combined momentum related to $m dx/dt + A(x)$. Thus, the sum of ((3a)) and ((3b)) are replaced by:

$$-i d/dx \sum_p b(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } p \text{ is not the momentum of the particle.}$$

Thus, the stochasticity inherent in the particle (even for a free particle) is combined with the stochasticity of $A(x) = \sum_k A_k \exp(ikx)$. Note: a free particle may be represented by $\exp(ip_1 x)$ for $x > x_0$ and 0 for $x \leq x_0$. In such a case, there is a step function and $\exp(ip_1 x)$ is not the same as the Fourier basis function $\exp(ip_1 x)$ which holds for all x .

All values of p then apply even if one has a free particle moving through a region with a magnetic potential $A(x)$ (which does not change the classical equations of motion). The free particle itself may be assigned a momentum p_1 , but this is an average value which is argued to be fluctuating. Thus, the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p b(p) \exp(ipx)$ is constructed of “free particle plus virtual photon” combinations $\exp(ipx)$ in such a manner that:

$$-i d/dx \sum_p b(p) \exp(ipx) = \langle p \text{ particle average} \rangle + A(x)$$

The form ((4)), however, is not usually presented even though it applies even to a particle with momentum p_1 (constant) moving through a region of $A(x)$. In particular, one would like to see the original p_1 wavefunction together with the explicit effects of $A(x)$ which one may guess are that of a phase buried within ((4)). Thus, we argue that one seeks a form: $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ i.e. a product form which is often used in solving the Schrodinger equation. The same approach may be used here. The time-independent Schrodinger equation is:

$$1/2m (p - A)(p - A) W = E \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } p \text{ is not the particle momentum operator}$$

A solution of ((5)) for a constant particle momentum of p_1 is: $W_0(x) = \exp(ip_1 x) \exp(i \int_0^x A(x_1) dx_1)$. Thus, $A(x)$ creates a distinct phase which may be measured in an experiment which compares a particle with momentum p_1 moving through a region with no $A(x)$ with one with p_1 moving through a region of $A(x)$ (where $A(x)$ does not change the equation of motion $p_1 = \text{constant}$).

If one considers only: $(p - A) W(x)$ one may see that $A(x)$ behaves like a potential yielding stochastic momentum hits to $W(x)$, but $p = -i d/dx$ acting on $W(x)$ brings down those same stochastic hits which create the fluctuation $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. p_1 and $-i d/dx \int_0^x A(x_1) dx_1$.

The point we wish to make is that stochasticity of $A(x) = \sum_k A_k \exp(ikx)$ leads to a phase directly related to this stochasticity (i.e. its integral over dx_1 from 0 to x).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that it is possible for velocity dependent potentials to yield no effect on the classical equations of motion and yet represent some physics present in the system. (In other words, the classical equations of motion do not uniquely determine a system even in the classical case.) For the quantum mechanical case, we argue there are stochastic hits which yield a fluctuating scenario represented by $P(p/x) = \exp(ipx)$. For a potential $V(x)$ or even the x portions of a velocity dependent potential, these may be written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ which yields stochastic hits creating a momentum distribution $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ at each x point. The question we examine in this note is: What does the "momentum" in $\exp(ipx)$ represent if a velocity dependent potential is present, especially one that does not affect the classical equations of motion? In such a case, the Lagrangian momentum $dL/d(dx/dt)$ contains mdx/dt as well as terms from the velocity dependent potential e.g. $A(x)$ from $A(x)dx/dt$. $A(x)$ as well as dx/dt represent fluctuations i.e. both are associated with $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Even if one has a constant particle momentum p_1 , one may imagine that this is an average with fluctuations leading to the $\exp(ip_1 x)$ form. One may note that $\exp(ip_1 x) x > x_0$ and 0 otherwise includes a step function and may be written in terms of a Fourier series.

Thus, one may use a form $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ where p represents a sum of the particle momentum and $A(x)$ and consider all different values of p . For a velocity dependent potential, the fluctuations of the particle are no longer sufficient and one needs to include the fluctuations in the field $A(x)$ as it is part of the Lagrangian momentum $dL/d(dx/dt)$. Alternatively, $mdx/dt dx/dt$ and the dx/dt part of $A(x)dx/dt$ both have a change related to $dt d/dt dx/dt$.

This scenario, however, should also be related to $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ where $W_1(x)$ represents the effects of $A(x)$ which may be separated off. If one considers the Hamiltonian $1/2m(p-A)(p-A)$ where $p = -i\hbar/dx$, one may find a separable solution $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ where $W_1(x) = \exp(i \int_{x_0}^x A(x_1) dx_1)$. This leads to an experimentally measurable phase, but we argue that $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(i \int_{x_0}^x A(x_1) dx_1)$ may be written as a Fourier series $\sum_p b(p) \exp(ipx)$ which shows the fluctuating nature of the system with p being a combination of particle momentum and $A(x)$ which is also fluctuating. Even if the particle has a constant momentum of p_1 , and may be represented as $\exp(ip_1 x)$ one may argue that this holds for $x > x_0$ and so there is a step function in the problem. Thus, $\exp(ip_1 x) x > x_0$ 0 $x \leq x_0$ is not the same as $\exp(ip_1 x)$ for all x .